

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LANGUAGE LEARNING AND CRITICAL THINKING OF EFL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between language learning and critical thinking of EFL learners. To achieve the purpose of the study, 68 female EFL learners were selected according to two different levels of study, beginner and intermediate to advanced groups in an institute in Kermanshah, a city in the west of Iran. They were requested to complete the "Watson-Glaser's Critical Thinking Appraisal". The data supported the theoretical expectation of a linkage between language learning and critical thinking of learners.

Key words: language learning, critical thinking

1. Introduction

Many years ago, it was believed that language learning can enhance intelligence of learners. The more it was exercised, the greater its abilities and the larger its assets. The way to increased mental power was to exercise the mind with complex and difficult tasks. Problem solving in mathematics, translation in foreign language classes, memorization, and so on were advocated learning activities (Chastain 1988).

According to Armstrong (1997) students scored considerably higher in math and language arts after one semester of foreign language study 90 minutes per week. As Hakuta (1986) said language learners show greater cognitive flexibility, better problem solving and higher order thinking skills. Numerous studies indicated that individuals who learn a second language are more creative and better at solving intricate problems than those who do not (Bamford and Mizokawa, 1991). Kiany (1988) explained personality as "one of the individual differences which is widely accepted as having an effect on learning in general and second language acquisition in particular". As mentioned, language learning can have positive impacts on personality traits. Critical thinking can be among those traits. One of the intellectual abilities which have been recognized as a determiner of learning is critical thinking. To succeed in language learning, critical thinking is one of the major competences for L2 learners (Connolly, 2000; Davidson, 1998; Davidson and Dunham, 1997). It's clear that critical thinking skills improve high order learning skills cause to higher level of language proficiency (Renner, 1996). The examination of distinction in human behavior is referred to as the study of individual dissimilarity. Kiany (1988) explained personality as "one of the individual differences which is widely accepted as having an effect on learning in general and second language acquisition in particular".

According to Ennis (2011) critical thinking is the ability to think clearly and rationally. It includes the ability to engage in reflective and independent thinking; the ability to decide what to do or what to believe. Halpern (1999) defines critical thinking as the use of cognitive skills or strategies that increase the probability of a desirable outcome. He argues that critical thinking is purposeful, reasoned, and goal-directed. It is the kind of thinking involved in solving problems, formulating inferences, calculating likelihoods, and making decisions.

2. Review of Literature

As Brookfield (1991) says "Critical Thinking involves recognizing and researching assumptions that undergird thoughts and actions (p 17)". He suggested that critical thinking entail research skills, being able to scrutinize the source of our knowledge, and how we use it in making decision. Scriven and Paul (2004) describe critical thinking as, "that mode of thinking about any subject, content, or problem in which the thinker improves the quality of his or her thinking by skillfully taking charge of the structures inherent in thinking and imposing intellectual standards upon them". This description comprise an attitudinal aspect of preference, and self-efficacy, and the met cognitive skill of estimating one's own thinking processes. Lately, Paul (1988) looked at critical thinking as learning how to ask and answer questions of analysis, combination and appraisal and "the ability to reach sound conclusions based on observations and information" (p. 50).

As Zhang (2003) said "The ideal critical thinker is habitually inquisitive, well-informed, trustful of reason, open-minded, flexible, fair-minded in evaluation, honest in facing personal biases, prudent in making judgments, willing to reconsider, clear about issues, orderly in complex matters, diligent in seeking relevant information, reasonable in the selection of criteria, focused in inquiry, and persistent in seeking results which are as precise as the subject and the circumstances the inquiry permit." (p. 1). "We understand critical thinking to be purposeful, self-regulatory judgment which results in interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference, as well as explanation of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criterion-logical, or contextual considerations upon which that judgment is based. Critical thinking is essential as a tool of inquiry. As such, critical thinking is a liberating force in education and a powerful resource in one's personal and civic life. While not synonymous with good thinking, critical thinking is a pervasive and a self-rectifying human phenomenon.

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3. Research Question and Hypotheses

1) Is there any relationship between language learning and critical thinking of Iranian EFL learners?

Based on the research question mentioned above, the following hypotheses emerged: There is no relationship between language learning and critical thinking.

4. Methodology

The participants of the present study were 68 female Iranian EFL students between the ages of 18 to 23. All of them had the same state, that is, their age, sex and their experience of language learning. These participants were two groups of EFL learners who studied in beginner and advanced levels in Khane Zaban Institute in Kermanshah. They were selected based on hierarchy of institute. The first group included 33 participants who were studying in beginner level and the second group included 35 participants who studied in intermediate to advanced level and their age varied from 18 to 23 years old. All the participants were studying at different academic fields. And also a randomization has been done to select the participant for beginner and intermediate to advanced groups.

To evaluate students' critical thinking ability, the Watson-Glaser Critical Thinking Appraisal (CTA) Form A was employed. Regarding validity, the Watson-Glaser test enjoys all areas of face, content, criterion and construction validity (Mirzai, 2012). In the present study, the Persian version of the

Watson-Glaser test, Form A (WGCTA-FA) was used to measure the participants' critical thinking. The test consists of five subsections, namely drawing inferences, recognizing assumptions, making deductions, interpreting evidence, and evaluating arguments, each comprising 16 items with two to five alternatives. The appraisal is not subject-specific and can be completed in 60 minutes. According to Mohammadyari (2002), this test and its subscales do have reliability and validity in Iranian culture. To analyze the reliability of the questionnaire, she utilized split-half reliability estimate. With the adapted version in Iran, the reliability was found to be 0.98 and the results of the factor analysis provided some support for the inventory hypothesized structure (Mohammadyari, 2002). The test-retest reliability of the original version of this critical thinking appraisal ($r = 0.81$) has been reported by (Glaser 1980), and the reliability coefficient of its Persian version has been estimated by Cronbach's Alpha to be ($\alpha = 0.85$) in (Faravani 2006). A composite scores for the five subscales of the test is obtained with values ranging from 0 to 80.

Table 4.1 summarizes the descriptive result of the Critical Thinking questionnaire.

Table 4.1. Descriptive statistics of EFL learners and their Critical Thinking

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
(B)CT	35	76.4286	8.4833
(A)CT	33	92.764	9.01020

As table 4.1 points, there is a significant difference between critical thinking of beginner and advanced learners. Therefore, the advanced group's Critical thinking ability ($m=76.4286$) was higher than that of the beginner group ($m=92.764$).

To answer the first research question, the critical thinking questionnaire was administered then Point-biserial correlation coefficient was used to analyze the data. The following table shows the correlation coefficient between EFL learning and critical thinking.

Table 4.2. Correlation coefficient between EFL learners and critical thinking

	CT (B)	CT (A)
(B) CT	Pearson Correlations	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.650**
		.000
68	N	68
(A) CT	Pearson Correlations	.650**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	68
	68	68

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As can be seen in table 4.2, there is a positive correlation between the two variables, $r = .65$, $n = 68$, $\text{sig} (2\text{-tailed}) = 0.01$, in a way that Learning English as a foreign language is associated with higher levels of critical thinking. This indicates that the null hypothesis can be rejected and there is a positive relationship between EFL learning and Critical Thinking of learners.

To examine the extent of correlation coefficient between the critical thinking of two groups, it is needed to ensure the existence of a linear correlation between the two variables. To this end, the following scatter plot was provided.

Figure 4.1 Critical Thinking of Advanced and Beginner Learners

According to Figure 4.1, there appears to be a positive linear correlation between the two variables, that is to say, learning a language is associated with higher levels of critical thinking.

5. Discussion and conclusion

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the possible relationship between EFL learning and critical thinking of learners. In a few words, as it showed the mean scores of the critical thinking questionnaire were higher in advanced group than beginner group. This confirms improvement in language learning has relation with critical thinking of learners. And also the results of the correlation analyses revealed that there is a positive relationship between language learning and critical thinking of learners. That is to say, the progression in EFL learning may have a positive influence on their critical thinking of learners.

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